

QUIZ

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice Mac 2011

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. All academic essays must contain _____.

References.¹

Themes.

Popular opinions.

Primary research.

2. Why is citation needed?

To show that the report is reliable.

To give credit to the author.

To avoid plagiarism, which is wrong and unethical.²

¹ EUCLID University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2019. 05. Accessed on January 03, 2020. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

² Ibid., 12.

To help readers in finding sources.

3. **Why is source analysis done?**

To find the most known source.

To find relevance and reliability of the source.³

To find unbiased sources.

To make the readers trust the report.

4. **What kind of drafting is recommended?**

Slow drafting.

Most comfortable drafting.⁴

Quick drafting.

Careful drafting.

5. **How do you number a note if the note applies to the entire chapter?**

Put footnote on each page.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 28.

⁴ Ibid., 48.

- Number the chapter title.
- Number the last sentence.
- Put an unnumbered footnote on the first page.⁵**

6. **Paranthesical citation typically consists of _____.**

- Author and page
- Author only.
- Author, date, and page.⁶**
- Author, date, page and title of the article.

7. **Why are secondary sources useful?**

- They combine knowledge from many primary sources and provide a quick overview of the topic.⁷**
- They are the original work of researchers.
- They are written by experienced authors.
- They are entirely reliable.

8. **What is meant by data interpretation?**

- It is categorizing the data.

⁵ Ibid., 96.

⁶ Ibid., 133.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 50.

- It is counting the data collected.
- It is reading through or beyond the findings.⁸**
- It is drawing a graph of the data.

9. **How do you decide when to stop sampling?**

- When no source is left to collect information.
- When no significant new information is emerging.⁹**
- When people offend interviews.
- When nobody responds to questions.

10. **What is meant by expert elicitation?**

- It is a structured approach to consulting experts.¹⁰**
- It is an interview conducted by an expert.
- It is reading books written by experts.
- It is an interview with the public.

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⁸ Ibid., 132.

⁹ Tracey Coates, "Belonging, Identities and Networks in Local Communities' Response to Flooding," n.d., 242..., 45.

¹⁰ Arjan Wardekker, *Climate Change Impact Assessment and Adaptation under Uncertainty* (S.l.: s.n., 2011), 25.

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